

Managing Editor's Column

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Here is another interesting "combined" issue of J.UCS.

The first part consists of four "regular" papers, i.e. papers which were reviewed and accepted by the members of our editorial board. The articles were written by authors from Slovenia, and South Africa and Spain. We thank the authors for submitting their articles to J.UCS and the reviewers for making the publication of the papers possible!

The second part of the issue features a selection of extended papers from the International Conference on Knowledge Management and Knowledge Technologies 2010 (I-KNOW 2010) held in Graz, Austria, September, 1-3, 2010. The first paper addresses Responsive Open Learning Environments (ROLE) which are understood as the next generation of Personal Learning Environments. ROLE represents an infrastructure on a global scale including learning management systems, institutions, and technologies. First experiences deploying ROLE at two higher learning institutions in different cultural settings proved the readiness of technology and benefits for students. The second paper discusses the convergence of interrelations among knowledge, innovation, and practices as critical factor to development of social action. The authors introduce the theory of convergence, advances in information systems development, and general requirements for pragmatic knowledge services. The last paper gives an overview on the nascent domain of mobile governance which among others covers initiatives as citizens' participation, public awareness, management of emergencies and crisis, provision of public services, and mobile phones as most ubiquitous communication device in recent years. We thank Gisela Granitzer for preparing the publication of these articles.

Hope you like what you find!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer, Managing Editor
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